

NUMERICAL MODELING OF FRACTURE IN TEXTILE COMPOSITES BY VTMS/BSAM AND RX-FEM

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ABSTRACT

The damage evolution and fracture of a textile double cantilever beam specimen was examined virtually through modeling. Each tow was modeled as a bundle of digital chains using a multi-chain digital element method (DEM). Each chain is defined as rigid in the transverse direction and can only be deformed in the axial direction. Adjacent neighboring digital elements are connected by a frictionless pin. The flexible digital chain is intended to represent real fibers. Two textile PMC numerical models were generated in this study using the Virtual Textile Morphology Suite (VTMS) with DEM technique. First, a two-layer of plain weave, double-cantilever beam (DCB) model was constructed. Second, a single adherend from the DCB was examined in tension/shear loading. In both cases, the initial configurations of textile fabric were first created. The numerical compacting process deformed the digital fibers further. The final tow geometry was then generated based on the distribution of the digital chains. This approach produced realistic fabric morphology through simulation of the compacting process as in a real textile forming process. In the DCB case, the delamination between tows and matrix, delamination between tows and tows were modeled by using regularized extended finite element method (Rx_FEM). The damage evolution in resin-rich regions was modeled using a continuum damage mechanics (CDM) approach. Both regularized X-FEM and CDM were formulated and implemented in the B-Spline Analysis Method (BSAM), a research finite element code. Additionally cracks inside of tows were modeled with mesh-independent cracks (MIC) for the single layer, plain weave PMC where MICs are kinematically modeled using the regularized X-FEM. The results show that the presented approach is able to simulate the crack propagating through the interfaces including tow-to-tow, tow-to-matrix, and layer-to-layer evolution as well as propagation inside the tow.

1 INTRODUCTION

Advanced textile composites materials provide an excellent opportunity to improve damage tolerance and impact resistance of traditional laminates by implementing out-of-plane reinforcements [1]. Textile composites have been considered promising materials in aerospace industry and are of great interest to other industries, such as automotive and wind energy. They offer designers a wide design space that includes the weave architecture, fiber/matrix materials, and processing methods. Developing material properties for design can be approached from many points of view. If a smearing of mechanical properties throughout specimen is acceptable, a generally anisotropic homogenized constitutive behavior can be obtained using simplified representations of the tow structure with enough simulation accuracy for preliminary and sometimes detailed design. However, the strength behavior of textile composites is not as amenable to these simplified homogenization techniques. Primarily empirical testing is employed to obtain strength and fracture design values. In many cases of 3D textile composite applications, the simple smearing approach is not satisfactory due to various and complex reinforcements. It poses an extremely complex analytical and computational problem.

Traditional laminate theory cannot be used for this purpose. However, computational insight into strength and damage propagation in these materials can still be achieved by introducing some reasonable simplifications [2].

High fidelity damage analysis in textile composites will depend on realistic representations of textile tow geometry, especially with respect to multi-layer textiles that experience tow nesting and compaction effects. This work will detail efforts at modelling damage evolution in two textile composite double-cantilever beams and a single plain woven sample. The textile tow morphologies were obtained through simulation of the compaction process using a multi-chain digital element technique in VTMS that allows the generation of textile morphology for a variety of textile architectures subjected to nesting and compaction effects. The resulting tow morphologies were then applied with a unique stress analysis methodology, which is capable of performing the robust analysis of complex textile composites. Currently, damage propagation was limited to matrix damage in the form of delamination between tows and matrix, delamination between tows, matrix cracking within the tows. Additional matrix damage in resin-rich zones was modelled with a continuum damage mechanics method.

Two textile DCB morphologies were examined to target the crack propagation through the mid plane. One DCB textile morphology consisted of two duplicated plain woven plies that were perfectly aligned. Each plain woven ply was virtually compacted separately and then assembled in alignment. The second DCB textile morphology also consisted of these two plies but with intentional nesting offset of $\frac{1}{4}$ of the tow spacing. A discrete, resin-rich layer between both adherends was added to the perfectly aligned DCB morphology to mimic the interface between the plies. One plain woven ply was also examined to demonstrate crack propagation through the tows and delamination around tows.

2 METHODOLOGY DESCRIPTION

2.1 Multi-Chain Digital Element for Tow Morphology

The Virtual Textile Morphology Suite (VTMS) is a multi-scale fabric morphology software developed by the University of Dayton Research Institute (UDRI) and the US Air Force Research Laboratory (AFRL). It starts to predict the distribution of digital fibers by simulating the fabric forming process and generates realistic tow geometry based on those deformed fibers. Besides common textile morphologies, it also can handle ply level geometry for laminates. The virtual fabric can be in various shapes (flat, curved, and tubular). Currently, VTMS is integrated with an in-house FEA software (BSAM) seamlessly and it also outputs the geometry results in multiple formats, which can be adopted by various commercial FEA tools, such as Abaqus, SolidWorks, etc. VTMS is based on the multi-chain digital element method, as described in [3,4], which is formulated to model realistic textile tow morphologies. In this methodology, a tow is represented as a number of filaments where each filament is a digital chain. A digital chain is composed of many rod-elements, defined as “digital elements”, as shown in Figure 1(a). Rotational nodes connect rod elements. It is thus able to represent a 1D flexible physical entity with a fixed cross-section, such as a fiber. When a digital chain approaches another digital chain, contact between two digital chains is represented by contact between nodes from two neighboring chains as shown in Figure 1(b) for the sake of simplicity and computational efficiency. If the distance between two nodes is smaller than the defined diameter of the digital chain, a contact element is added between them. When contact occurs between two nodes, two physical conditions are also considered: sticking and sliding, which are all governed by the normal force between nodes and the defined friction coefficients. Each chain is assigned with an initial tension, and the system is allowed to relax through a series of iterative solutions. The multi-chain digital element method was used in this work to obtain realistic textile tow morphology.

Additionally, a vacuum bag or hard mold may be simulated using the multi-chain digital element method. To accomplish this, networks of rod elements are connected via nodes. The stiffness of the vacuum bag is controlled by the stiffness of the rods. A hard mold is enabled by fully constraining the nodes [5,6]. External loads can be applied to nodes directly. Figure 2 shows a deformed bundle of digital fibers and a virtual plain woven under vacuum bagging compaction.

Figure 1: Schematic of a single digital chain (a) and a contact element between chains

Figure 2: A deformed bundle of digital fibers (a) and a compacted plain weave (b).

2.2 Independent Mesh Method for Tow-Matrix Interface

In the Independent Mesh Method (IMM), all tows and the matrix are meshed independently of each other [7]. While those meshes are combined together to reassemble the textile composite, much of the matrix has been already occupied by the tows. In the IMM, the shape functions of the matrix displacement approximations are reduced by excluding all functions entirely covered by tows and modifying the integration domain of the shape functions partially covered by tows. The integration domain of the interface element, which is partially covered by the tow, is the remaining volume after subtracting the tow volume from whole element and is addressed by Gauss integration points of this remaining volume. Each vertex of the matrix mesh is characterized as either matrix or tow by using the Marching Cubes Algorithm [8]. The algorithm scans through all matrix elements one by one, and then determines which node belongs to the matrix and which node belongs to the tow. The locations of tow surfaces that intercept the matrix element are recorded as interface points (Figure 3a). Through examination of all the interface points and matrix nodes, the remaining volume can then be extracted and decomposed to a group of tetrahedrons (Figure 3b). The principal of the decomposition algorithm [9] is to find the smallest circum-sphere of an existing boundary triangle and a nearby point (Figure 3c). The circum-sphere should not contain points other than those four vertices. If such a circum-sphere exists, a new tetrahedron is constructed and its surface facets (triangles) are added to a list of triangles. Internal triangles are removed from the list every time new triangles are added. The process of searching for the new tetrahedron stops when the end of the list is reached. In cases where collinear or coplanar points exist, an algorithm jiggles these points to remove degeneracy by inducing a small, random displacement to the point. Gauss integration points and weight factors for each tetrahedron are calculated and mapped to the interface element (Figure 4) [10]. All connections between tows and matrix are applied by using a penalty method or cohesive zone interface addressed in Ref. [7].

Figure 3: Volume subtraction of interface element and tetrahedralization

Figure 4 : 2D schematic of Gauss integration point in an interface element (a) and remaining matrix volume after volume subtraction (b)

2.3 Discrete Damage Model for Tow Crack Propagation

The cohesive zone delamination propagation model can be extended to the regularized MIC formulation [11,12]. In BSAM, the fracture energy is calculated at each integration point of the cracked zone. The total fracture energy of the crack is the combination of contributions from nearby elements. Thus, the fracture energy is a function of the displacement jump and ties together the otherwise independent displacement approximations in the cracked zones. In these methods the displacement discontinuity associated with cracking is modeled by changing the finite element kinematics and adding additional degrees of freedom in the displacement approximation to represent localized damage, rather than reducing the stiffness properties as in CDM. The cracked element has double the number of degrees of freedom of the non-cracked initial element, providing independent displacement approximations on each of the partitioned regions. One can consider the Rx-FEM as an element duplication method as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Schematic of duplicated cracked elements

A 3-zone method is developed to describe the cohesive zone crack. Each crack zone is divided by zone '1' (color blue) and zone '2' (color red) in a finite crack region, which is further encapsulated by a narrower band of zone "0" (color white) to insulate itself from other cracked regions. The 3-zone method is able to model multiple cracks in the same structure. Crack propagation starts from a seed cell, which can be determined by a failure criterion, at which a MIC crack is inserted. Propagation of this crack depends on the cohesive zone definition. When a neighboring cell is entitled to be a next crack cell (either through propagation or new initiation), this cell and its neighboring cells will be added to the cell list. The whole process will stop when there are no more cells left to visit. Cracks can be propagated through the specimens with arbitrary shape. Figure 6 shows the results of crack propagation in a two-ply curved laminates using the 3-zone method. As we can see, cracks propagate from the seed cell to all connected cells (neighboring elements) until reaching the boundaries. The cracks will not go over the boundaries to extend to another ply. To simulate crack growth and turning, the crack can only be allowed to propagate at a finite length for each step. Crack turning occurs only at cells, which are immediately near the crack tips.

Figure 6: Crack propagation by 3-zone method

2.3 Continuum Damage Mechanics Model for Matrix Damage

FE implementation of CDM methodology results in representing all forms of damage as local stiffness reduction in individual elements, i.e. the effects of matrix and fiber damage are described by directionally reducing the stiffness properties of affected elements [13]. The degree of stiffness reduction in this approach is dependent on both the fracture toughness of the composite and the mesh size. These difficulties transpire from the nature of CDM where the damage, namely, the local

displacement discontinuity, which it introduces in the material, is not modeled explicitly and instead replaced by its effect on stiffness in the homogenized sense. Figure 7 describes the proposed response of the matrix, where σ is the maximum principal stress. The damage variable is defined based on the stress strain relationship.

Figure 7: Schematic of the proposed resin uniaxial response described in Maimi et al [13]

3 TEXTILE COMPOSITE MODELING PROCEDURE

3.1 Virtual Fiber Preform Construction

An embedded template in VTMS was used to generate an initial, idealized, single plain weave preform, with warp tow and weft tow spacing of 1 mm. Each tow was discretized into 54 filaments, which represent approximately 7500 IM7 fibers. The preform was assigned boundary conditions and subjected to a serial of virtual relaxations, resulting in the redistribution of fibers to a natural state accounting for initial filament tension. A virtual vacuum bag was then applied to cover the woven preform and compact the preform in the thickness direction. A virtual rigid platen was also used in the simulation to support the woven preform. In this manner, a single adherend was created. Selected steps are shown in Figure 8. This fabric woven preform was used as a basis for production of the both DCB models and the single woven specimen model.

In the perfectly aligned DCB case, two instances of the single preform layer were stacked with the platen sides together and the warp and weft tows aligned. To facilitate a clean fracture plane between the two adherends in the damage modeling, a gap of 0.04 mm of filled resin was intentionally inserted between the two fiber preform adherends. In this way, resin-rich region damage evolution could be allowed as well as the comparison of behavior between an aligned and offset nested DCB. Final preform thickness was approximately 0.75 mm.

Figure 8: Procedure of compacted plain woven layer from idealized textile pattern to discretization to relaxation and to final compaction.

The offset nested DCB preform was produced in a similar manner. In this case, however, the curved, vacuum bag side of the initial preform was stacked together. The top preform adherend was then shifted by $\frac{1}{4}$ of a tow spacing (i.e. 0.25 mm) in the X-direction intentionally. As similarly to the perfect aligned DCB case, a 0.04 mm thick virtual flexible platen was also inserted between the two preforms before the compacting near the left origin of the DCB specimen. Two virtual rigid platens (one on the top, one on the bottom) were used to compact the preforms until a same thickness of 0.75 mm was reached. The 0.04mm virtual platen served to separate the two adherends in the region near the left specimen origin and facilitated meshing an initial crack in the subsequent FE solutions. Figure 9 shows a side-view comparison between the two DCB fiber preforms

Figure 9 Side view comparison of aligned and offset nested DCB virtual preform.

3.2 FE Model Details

Extraction of solid representations of the tows in VTMS was described in Ref. [14]. These solid representations were further clipped to dimensions of 7 mm in the X-direction and 2 mm in the Z-direction. The resulting solids were then meshed with hexahedral solid H-elements within VTMS. In both DCB cases, a hexahedral H-element mesh for the resin was produced using a third party meshing tool known as Gmsh [15] with dimensions 7 mm in X, 2 mm in Z, and 1.3 mm in Y. The resin mesh included a notch with dimensions of 1.5 x 0.04 x 2.0 mm in X, Y, and Z. Figure 10 shows the final products of DCM model created in VTMS. For the single plain woven case, the resin zone was simply defined as rectangular box meshed with hexahedral H-elements.

Figure 10: Various views of perfect aligned DCB specimen with a notch added

Material properties were assigned to the textile tows and matrix pockets according to Table 1. All tows were connected to matrix and to each other via cohesive zone interfaces of the formulation described in [8] with $G_c = 0.177 \text{ N/mm}$ and $Y_t = 77.0 \text{ N/mm}^2$. Boundary conditions for both DCB specimens were applied as follows. Incremental displacements were specified at $X=0$ for the top adherend in the positive Y-direction and in the negative Y-direction for the bottom adherend. At $Z=0$ and $Z=2 \text{ mm}$, $U_z=0$. At $X=0$, $U_x=0$ at the top corner nodes in the upper adherend and at the bottom corner nodes of the lower adherend. For the single plain woven composite, the axial displacement and schematic of boundary conditions are applied. The specimen measured 7mm in the warp direction,

3mm in the weft direction, and was 0.375mm thick. Material properties used for the single plain woven composite were the same as shown in Table 1. The specimen was loaded via an axial (warp direction) tensile load with a small transverse (weft direction) shearing load as shown in Figure 13.

Property	Composite (IM7/5250-4)	Resin (5250-4)
E_{11} (N/mm ²)	1.65×10^5	3.45×10^3
E_{22}, E_{33} (N/mm ²)	1.03×10^4	
G_{13}, G_{12} (N/mm ²)	5.79×10^3	1.28×10^3
G_{23} (N/mm ²)	3.31×10^3	
ν_{13}, ν_{12}	0.56	0.35
ν_{23}	0.31	

Table 1: Tow (IM7/5250-4) and resin properties (5250-4)

The AFRL FE code known as BSAM was used to analyze all three specimen geometries. Both rX-FEM and CDM schemes were used for propagation of matrix damage in resin pockets between adherends for both the aligned and offset nested DCB specimens. The Rx-FEM cohesive zone scheme, as described in above, was also used for MIC within tows, delamination between tows and tows, and delamination between tows and matrix. Damage propagation by Rx-FEM in current version of BSAM can only be allowed to follow the fiber orientations within tows and at predefined planes, i.e. the midplane in DCB cases. The properties used in all cohesive for Rx-FEM cracks and delaminations were the same. The properties for CDM were set as $Y_T=77.0$ N/mm², $Y_C=77.0$ N/mm², $G_{YT}=0.177$ N/mm, $f_{YT}=0.1$, $f_{GT}=0.6$.

4 RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Figure 11(a) displays the results of load-displacement behaviors for both damage schemes in the perfect aligned DCB case. Also shown in the Figure 11(b) is a deformed view of the DCB specimen, which shows the X component of stress and the Rx-FEM damage plane. Resin damage propagation for both damage schemes appear to agree quite well. An initially linear portion of the load-displacement curve is followed by a series of load drops and load increases. The location of these features is associated with the location of the resin damage zone with respect to the weft-tow locations. The damage zone approaches the centerline of each weft tow slowly with an accompanying rise in load. As the resin damage passes the centerline of each weft tow, the load rapidly decreases until the damage approaches the next weft tow.

(a)

(b)

Figure 11: (a) Load-displacement curve comparison of rX-FEM and CDM for aligned DCB specimen and (b) Deformed X component of stress with damage propagation in red (resin not shown for clarity)

A comparison of load-displacement behavior between aligned and nested DCB specimens is shown in Figure 12. While showing similar trends, the Rx-FEM nested prediction is significantly smoother than the Rx-FEM aligned prediction; while the CDM nested prediction displays slightly higher loads throughout the loading range. These differences in the nested predictions are believed to be due to the constrained nature of the Rx-FEM damage plane. That is, a single plane was defined that allowed the resin to fail only at the midplane of the DCB specimens and at the interfaces between tows. This overly restricts the nature of the failure progression, while the CDM resin propagation failure allows the resin to fail naturally and in concert with the delamination around the tows. Further efforts with additional nesting configurations and matching experimental efforts will help to understand the differences in prediction techniques.

Figure 13 shows the results of Rx-FEM damage propagation within the tows for the single plain woven composite with the matrix not shown for clarity. A schematic of the boundary conditions is also shown in the figure. The specimen was loaded via an axial (warp direction) tensile load with a small transverse (weft direction) shearing load. Transverse matrix cracking in the weft tows is clearly visible as displacement discontinuities in the figure with the cracks highlighted in red. Failure in the matrix, not shown, was clearly visible. Delamination damage and fiber fracture were also present. The specimen failed completely through the largest area of fiber damage on the next load step.

Figure 12: Load-displacement behavior from both DCB specimens with both resin damage propagation schemes

Figure 13: Multi-Crack propagation in a single plain woven layer (resin not shown for clarity)

5 CONCLUSIONS

Multiple different techniques were combined to produce numerical model results for one single plain woven composite and two textile DCB configurations (a perfectly aligned DCB specimen and an offset nested DCB specimen). Realistic tow geometries were obtained using the VTMS

powered by the multi-chain digital element technique. Stress analysis was accomplished through the BSAM with IMM capability. Delamination around tows was modeled via a standard cohesive zone method. Transverse cracking within a tow was modeled with an Rx-FEM method. Finally, resin-rich zone damage was modeled using either an Rx-FEM crack plane method or a CDM method. Both resin-rich zone damage techniques worked well, especially for the aligned specimen that contained a clean fracture plane between the two adherends. The non-predictive nature of defining an Rx-FEM cracking plane, however, may be cause for concern, especially for more complex textile configurations. Reliance on the CDM approach appears to be viable until a self-guided Rx-FEM damage propagation scheme can be implemented.

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